

**ПОСЛЕДСТВИЕ ХРОНИЧЕСКОГО ГЛАМЕРУЛОНЕФРИТА У
ДЕТЕЙ, СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ РЕШЕНИЕ**

Базарова Нигина Собиржановна

Доцент кафедры Организация фармацевтического дела.

Самаркандский государственный медицинский университет.

Почта: Bozorovanigina72@gmail.com ORCID 0009-0006-1391-0283

Бобокулова Шохиста

Студент 5курса Фармацевтического факультета СамГМУ

Аннотация

Распространенность гломерулонефрита среди детей составляет 7–20,5 на 100000 детского населения. В структуре заболеваний почек у взрослых хронический гломерулонефрит составляет большой процент, заложенный в детском возрасте. Нефритический синдром – одно из тяжелых синдромов заболеваний почек у детей, отличающийся развитием осложнений и инвалидности, впоследствии приводящих к большим финансовым затратам, гемодиализу и пересадке почек. В этом плане важную роль играет протеинурический синдром, который относится к тяжелым вариантам гломерулопатий у детей.

Ключевые слова: Гломерулонефрит, нефритический синдром, прогноз, МКБ-10.

**CONSEQUENCES OF CHRONIC GLAMERULONEPHRITIS IN
CHILDREN, MODERN SOLUTIONS.**

Bazarova Nigina Sobirzhanovna

Associate PhD of the Department

of Organization of Pharmaceutical Business.

Samarkand State Medical University,

Mail: Bozorovanigina72@gmail.com ORCID 0009-0006-1391-0283

Bobokulova Shohista

5th year student of the Faculty of Pharmacy of SamSMU.

Annotation

The prevalence of glomerulonephritis among children is 7–20.5 per 100,000 children. In the structure of kidney diseases in adults, chronic glomerulonephritis makes up a large percentage, starting in childhood. Nephritic syndrome is one of the severe syndromes of kidney disease in children, characterized by the development of complications and disability, subsequently leading to large financial costs, hemodialysis and kidney transplantation. In this regard, proteinuric syndrome plays an important role, which refers to severe variants of glomerulopathies in children.

Key words: Glomerulonephritis, nephritic syndrome, prognosis, ICD-10.

Relevance of the problem. Chronic nephritic syndrome is characterized by micro/macrohematuria, moderate proteinuria (up to 1 g/day), dense edema, and hypertension. This is a large group of primary and secondary glomerulonephritis. Nephritic syndrome is a manifestation of glomerular inflammation (glomerulonephritis), which occurs at any age; its causes depend on age, and its mechanisms depend on the cause.

In the currently valid ICD 10th revision, chronic nephritic syndrome is assigned code N 03. The morphological classification of chronic nephritic syndrome according to ICD-10 according to changes in the nephrobiopsy suggests the following conditions: N03.0 - chronic nephritic syndrome, minor glomerular disorders; N 03.1 – chronic nephritic syndrome, focal and segmental glomerular lesions; N03.2 – chronic nephritic syndrome, diffuse membranous

glomerulonephritis; N03.3 – chronic nephritic syndrome, diffuse mesangial proliferative glomerulonephritis; N03.4 – chronic nephritic syndrome, diffuse endocapillary proliferative glomerulonephritis; N03.5 – chronic nephritic syndrome, diffuse mesangiocapillary glomerulonephritis; N03.6 – chronic nephritic syndrome, dense sediment disease; N03.7 – chronic nephritic syndrome, diffuse crescentic glomerulonephritis; N03.8 – chronic nephritic syndrome, other changes; N03.9 – chronic nephritic syndrome, unspecified change.

Over the last decade, the prevalence of the disease has shown a significant increase, amounting to 36.76% in the structure of nephrological pathology. In the structure of kidney diseases in children hospitalized in the nephrology department, glomerulonephritis takes second place. Based on the results of the analysis of the results of scientific research, the mechanism of occurrence of glomerular pathology, a genetic defect in the T-cell component of the immune system, expressed in one form or another, are considered as the main cause of disruption of the antigenic structure, including activation of the immune system due to a pathological reaction with the subsequent formation of immune complexes. Then the formed complexes settle in the tissues and trigger a whole cascade of immunopathological processes, which involve tissue phagocytosis cells and elements of the T-cell immunity. These processes, in turn, activate the enzymes of lysosomes of damaged cells with disruption of the basement membrane. The prerequisite is a decrease in the number of T-lymphocytes, as a result of which an irreversible process starts.

The emergence of a proinflammatory phenotype in a large number of cells at once determines the influence of their network interaction on the development of tissue stress, for example, due to the formation of a network of cytokines. Pro-inflammatory tissue stress manifests itself in a variety of ways, and they are all fundamentally different. But at the same time, the same signaling pathways are found in cells involved in various types of inflammation and proinflammatory

processes . These processes include various types of activated cells, the decisive role of which belongs to the cells of the immune system; untimely diagnosis and delayed treatment most often cause the progression of the disease and the development of chronic renal failure, followed by delayed growth and development of the child, disability, and a significant shortening of life.

According to modern literature, endogenous creatinine serves as a unit of measurement for the functional activity and filtration activity of the kidneys. The study of creatinine as a marker of glomerular filtration rate began in 1926 with the publication of Paul Brandt Rehberg's article "Studies of Renal Function. Rate of filtration and reabsorption in the human kidney." Since then the use of creatinine has become a vital element in clinical medicine.

In modern medicine, molecular diagnostics, which is based on the immunological method of recognizing specific DNA segments, is widely used to identify and determine the concentration of the desired substance in laboratory analysis. In molecular diagnostics, DNA recognition is more common and popular, which is the polymerase chain reaction (PCR) method. This technique has found application in the determination of antigens, antibodies and DNA.

PCR allows you to determine in the studied set sections of genetic information, the individual sequence of human DNA nucleotides among a large number of other DNA sections and multiply it many times. PCR can be conditionally defined as a biochemical reaction for the synthesis of genetic information in a cell " *in vitro* ".

Currently, thanks to modern technologies in medicine, fundamental scientific principles are emerging, and therefore there is a need for intensive development of methods for the molecular diagnosis of kidney diseases, expanding the generally accepted traditional methods and providing additional information and insight into molecular pathophysiology. According to forecasts, the identification of genes and their changes during the disease process, which predict the course of the

disease, are becoming increasingly important in the process of diagnosing diseases of the urinary system. The prognosis of the disease included changes in chromosomal polymorphic genes of matrix metalloproteinase and its tissue inhibitors, as well as the manifestation of these changes in chronic glomerulonephritis.

Intensive progress in the field of molecular diagnostics of kidney diseases reveals a separate huge direction in medicine - “molecular nephropathology ” . Subsequent research into kidney diseases from the point of view of molecular nephropathology will make it possible to study the pathogenesis of a number of kidney diseases from a different perspective and create a platform for solving many unresolved questions about personalized therapy that takes into account the molecular and genetic aspects of the course of the disease in a specific individual patient .

There are some kidney diseases that lead to disability and deterioration in the quality of life of patients. First of all, this is due to the importance of the functional activity of the kidneys and the removal of metabolic waste products. The main pathogenetic mechanism of chronic glomerulonephritis is considered to be the launch of systemic inflammatory immunity with subsequent hyperproduction of elements of oxidative stress, as well as a change in the balance of the “proteolysis-antiproteolysis” system, which enhances tissue remodeling and related processes .

An analysis of the scientific literature of recent years reliably indicates the importance of molecular diagnostics and the increasingly widespread introduction of molecular diagnostic methods into clinical practice for diagnosing kidney diseases. Despite the numerous scientific works over the past few decades devoted to a detailed study of the pathogenesis of chronic glomerulonephritis, in modern nephrology there is no clearly defined idea about the mechanism of development of this disease and, accordingly, there is no single consensus among

scientists about its pathogenesis. Ongoing research in this area has demonstrated the role of genetic factors in the development of chronic glomerulonephritis, but the development of new tests has been very slow. Fast, effective and accurate methods for early diagnosis, as well as predicting the consequences of kidney diseases in pediatric practice, are a priority for the scientific community. However, the number of studies on molecular biology in the pathogenesis of chronic glomerulonephritis in sick children is still small, and their results contradictory. Therefore, in support for many years this question remains unresolved.

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